

Understanding Current Indian Agriculture

A Step Towards Self-reliance Bharat by 2047

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Abstract

Development of Indian agriculture is of paramount importance for India's dream of becoming a developed nation by 2047. India has the largest agricultural land in the world, a self-reliant model of agricultural export is required to make India one of the top three economies of the world. One of the fundamental aspects to be studied in this regard is our current operational practices and their limitations, which involves combining the thirty thousand feet view with the ground realities. As per the Agricultural Census 2015-2016, 78% of indigenous farmers are small and marginal, having less than 1 hectare (2.5 acres) of land. This is one of the fundamental reasons for agribusiness to remain as an unorganized sector. This leads to high dependence on labour which is decreasing day by day making agribusiness more challenging for small and marginal farmers. The scope of this research paper is limited to studying the current operational aspects.

Key Words: Indian Agriculture, Self Reliance Bharat, Operational Efficiency, Supply Chain

1. Introduction

To understand the operational aspects in agriculture, it is essential to understand the current practices being followed by the indigenous farmers. The details of classification of land and irrigated area in India are tabulated below [2].

Table-1 - Classification of Land area in India

	Classification of Land	Area (Thousand Ha)
1	Forest	72,011
2	Area put to non-agriculture uses	27,344
3	Barren & unculturable land	17,168
4	Permanent pastures & other grazing lands	10,376
5	Culturable Waste Land	12,219
6	Land under Misc. tree Crops	3,154
7	Fallow Land Other than Current Fallows	11,633
8	Current Fallow	14,531
9	Net Area Sown	139,351
	Agriculture Land (5+6+7+8+9)	180,888
	Cultivated Land (8+9)	153,882
	Cropping Intensity (% of Total cropped Area over net Area Sown)	141.6%

Table-2 - Classification of Irrigated area in India

	Irrigated Area	Area (Thousand Ha)
1	Government Canals	16,264
2	Private Canals	165
3	Total Canals (1+2)	16,429
4	Tanks	1,668
5	Tube wells	34,708

	Irrigated Area	Area (Thousand Ha)
6	Other wells	11,042
7	Other Sources	7,707
	Net Irrigated Area (3+4+5+6+7)	71,554
	Gross Irrigated Area	102,667
	% Of Gross Irrigated Area over Gross Cropped Area	52.03 %
	% Of Net Irrigated Area over Net Area Sown	51.35 %

Figure 1 : Agricultural Exports from India (US\$ Billion)

2. Current Operations

2.1 Seed Supply

The usual sources of seed supply for existing farmers are; their grains/pulses stored in the previous year, seeds purchased from the market or provided by the government at subsidized rates. Seeds purchased from the government or market have test certificates. Farmers are not getting their seeds of the previous year lab tested which they want to use this year. Moreover, purchasing seeds is a time-consuming activity for farmers.

One of the most important elements in raising agricultural output in any farming system is the use of high-quality seeds. By connecting with a reputable seed merchant, the participating farmers from both pilot sites gained advantages. Since it was a big order that nearly seemed like it was placed by a single entity, the seed merchant agreed to transport the seed straight to their community. [1] Since only 4 to 5 kg of seed would be needed for 0.2 acres, these farmers would have to rely on larger farmers for cooperation or on village seed traders, who charged more and were unable to guarantee germination or quality. [1]

2.2 Land Preparation for Sowing

Three activities before sowing of seeds: Ploughing, Levelling and Fertilization. Generally, small and marginal farmers hire tractors, cultivators (old technology, locally made) from big farmers for these activities. At present ploughing is up to a depth of 4" to 9", however continuous use of chemical fertilizers has filled the soil with chemicals. To move towards sustainable farming, soil regeneration and water retention is required and for this deep ploughing can be helpful. Present equipment's have limitations of ploughing depth. Agricultural field levelling is done using visual method without using engineering equipment's which leads to uneven ground slope. This is affecting the uniform distribution of irrigation water in the field. Organic manure or chemical fertilizers are being used based on farmers discretion without soil testing, due to which either excess or less amount of manure gets mixed in the soil, causing productivity and related health problems.

The diminishing size of farms makes mechanization which is essential for increasing agricultural productivity and production while lowering costs—even less feasible. States in India that have more access to advanced machinery and mechanical power are more productive

than other states, claim Singh et al. (2014). However, when economic resources are scarce and landholdings are tiny and dispersed, it might be difficult to reap the benefits of mechanization. It is against economies of scale to mechanize tiny and non-contiguous groupings of small farms, particularly for tasks like harvesting and land preparation (Mehta et al., 2019). As the average farm size continues to decline, more farms will be placed in the negative category, making it increasingly unfeasible for individuals to purchase agricultural equipment. Additionally, the bulk of Indian farmers lack the resources necessary to purchase farm machinery due to its high cost. Another significant barrier to greater mechanization is the reluctance of commercial banks to finance agricultural equipment. Additionally, after-sales service presents a problem because most villages lack conveniently accessible equipment maintenance centers due to the remoteness of rural areas (FICCI, 2015). [1]

Table 3 : Impact of Climate Change on Indian Agriculture

Crop	Impact	Reference
Rice	3-15% yield reduction with 1.5°C temperature increase and 2 mm decrease in precipitation	Ahluwalia and Malhotra, 2006
Wheat	5-10% yield reduction with every 1°C increase in temperature	IPCC, 2001
Maize	10-40% yield reduction with temperature increase	Byjesh et al., 2010
Sorghum	50% yield reduction due to climate change	Shukla et al., 2023

Table 4 : Climate Change Projections for Indian Agriculture

Timeframe	Temperature Increase	Precipitation Change	Reference
2070-2099	2-5°C	Variable	Shukla et al., 2023
2080s	2-4°C	7-10% increase	IPCC, 2007

Table 5: Adaptation and Mitigation Strategies

Strategy	Description	Reference
Adjustment in sowing dates	No-cost decision to adapt to climate change	Shukla et al., 2023
Breeding resilient crops	Develop crops that can withstand climate variability	Aggarwal, 2008
Agronomic practices	Improve soil management and irrigation	Srinivasarao et al., 2016

Table 6: Vulnerability of Indian Agriculture

Region	Vulnerability	Reference
North Indian states	Highly susceptible to climate change	World Bank, 2008
Coastal regions	Vulnerable to inundation and salinization	Shukla et al., 2023
Rainfed agriculture	Most impacted by climate change	Shukla et al., 2023

2.3 Seed Sowing

Seed sowing is done using manual labour or seed drill machine (locally manufactured). Manual labour process is time consuming, has challenges like maintaining seed spacing, adhering to sowing schedule due to unavailability of labour etc. Seed drill machine is also hired or owned, which also causes problems related to accuracy of spacing in seed sowing process.

2.4 Irrigation

About 51.35% of the net sown area in India [Table 2] is irrigated by water wells and canals. The remaining area is irrigated by rainwater. Irrigation water in right quantity at right time with uniform coverage of irrigated area is essential for crop growth and productivity. Soil moisture, atmospheric humidity and temperature are essential measurements that define irrigation

requirements which are not an integral part of agriculture at present. Sprinklers are efficient irrigation devices for uniform distribution of water, with volume control, which are not being used on a large scale. Rainwater irrigation is entirely dependent on rainfall and accuracy of weather forecast.

The dry season of 2017–18 was the third season of the SFLF pilot. Taraboisan Village farmers continued their SFLF farming during this season, but Khanizpur farmers were unable to do so due to a lack of irrigation during the dry season. [1]

2.5 Fertilizer/Pesticide/Weed Spraying

Fertilizers are generally sprayed for the second time (before first sowing) on the belief that it improves crop growth and grain size and colour look good. The more fertilizer, the higher the crop growth, is the dominant belief. Pesticides are used in anticipation of pest growth as per experience or when pests appear, however, pest forecast prediction mechanism is not available considering climatic conditions and other relevant factors. Weed control chemicals are used to remove weeds. Locusts are extremely dangerous for crops as they affect the entire village. Pesticides are available, but their use is too much to reduce the impact of locusts. Providing timely warning for locust movement may be the best solution. Currently there is no such system.

The participants disclosed that they had trouble purchasing urea, diammonium phosphate (DAP), and potash during the previous seasons because to their high cost and delayed availability. The fertilizer was extremely costly for the farmers since it had to go through a number of players and stakeholders in the supply chain, including small dealers at the block level, district-level wholesale distributors, and company-run wholesale outlets, before arriving at the local dealer. According to the Khanizpur hamlet's female farmers, their village input shop rarely had fertilizer on hand during most seasons. On occasion, they would ask their husbands to get it from the block's larger market, but it would still not arrive in time. [1]

2.6 Harvesting and Threshing

When the crop is ripe and manually inspected by the farmer, harvesting begins. Earlier there was manual harvesting, but now harvesting machines are available on rent and small/marginal farmers use them. Harvesting is done as per the affordability of paying rent and availability of machine. The decision of crop ripeness is taken by the farmer based on his own experience without any laboratory testing, which may potentially lead to harvesting of grain with high moisture content. Currently manual crop protection system is used, which has its own limitations.

Without the use of middlemen at the village level, both wheel-operated and chain-operated harvesters were rented straight from the district-level service provider for the two dry seasons. However, only chain-operated combine harvesters were utilized during the rainy season because wheel-operated combine harvesters are challenging to operate on slushy soil after rain. [1]

3. Supply Chain of Foodgrains / Pulses etc

Foodgrains generally have three destinations: Government MSP Procurement Centres - Government has set up Agricultural Produce Market Committees (APMCs)/Temporary Procurement Centres/Aggregation Centres. These are for fixed time period and farmers should sell their produce with prior appointment and meeting the quality (moisture in grain). If the quality is not met then the farmer should reschedule his appointment for sale.

Local Mandi/Market - Co-operative societies where farmers can sell to buyers or brokers at negotiated price. Depending on the cash flow requirement of the farmer they can sell foodgrains at prices other than MSP, including distress sales.

Storage with farmers - Farmers can store foodgrains at their stores and sell as per their convenience or when they get the right price.

India is wasting 15-20% of wheat/pulses at this stage of agriculture. Without any negotiating leverage, Khanizpur's farmers could only sell their meager harvest to the village middlemen. As tenant farmers, they were required to donate half of their harvest to their owners. The other half would be saved for their own use, and the excess would be sold. Effective price negotiating was never feasible in the past when they dealt with village traders individually for a relatively modest amount of production. Additionally, because the land title was not in their names, these farmers were unable to access the Kisan Mandai. Millions of small and marginal farmers in India are already at a disadvantage due to diseconomies of scale and a lack of bargaining power in input and output markets; the situation has gotten worse due to the growing labor shortage and quickly rising wage rates. [1, 2]

Challenges in Indian Agriculture Supply Chain [12]

- **Fragmented Land Holdings:** Small and marginal farmers face difficulties in accessing markets and achieving economies of scale.
- **Insufficient Market Infrastructure:** Lack of proper storage, transportation, and warehousing facilities leads to post-harvest losses.
- **Weak Bargaining Power:** Farmers are often exploited by middlemen due to limited market access and information asymmetry.
- **High Transaction Costs:** Inefficient supply chains result in increased costs for farmers and consumers.
- **Quality Degradation:** Poor handling and storage practices lead to quality degradation of agricultural produce.

Key Issues in Agri-Food Supply Chain Management [12,13]

- **Supply Chain Inefficiencies:** Inefficient supply chains lead to wastage, poor price realization, and lack of transparency.
- **Limited Access to Finance:** Farmers and small-scale enterprises face difficulties in accessing formal credit and financial services.
- **Lack of Standardization:** Absence of standardization in agricultural commodities leads to quality variations and pricing issues.
- **Inadequate Market Information:** Limited access to market information hinders farmers' ability to make informed decisions.
- **Post-Harvest Losses:** Inefficient handling and storage practices result in significant post-harvest losses.

Opportunities for Improvement [12]

- **Technology Adoption:** Leveraging technology can improve supply chain efficiency, transparency, and access to market information.
- **Contract Farming:** Contract farming can provide farmers with better price realization and reduced market risks.
- **Refrigerated Warehousing:** Improved warehousing facilities can reduce post-harvest losses and provide farmers with better price realization.
- **Public-Private Partnerships:** Collaboration between public and private sectors can improve supply chain infrastructure and services.
- **Capacity Building:** Training and capacity building programs can enhance farmers' skills and knowledge, improving their bargaining power and market access.

4. Conclusion

Indian agriculture operations are lagging at every stage, which requires reform factors of seamless integration with the organized sector and institutional approach, aimed at doubling farmers' income. Inherent limitations from operations in mostly small farms, falling graph of labour availability, potential impact, economies of scale, difficulties in adopting supply chain technology, testing, integrated 3 & 4 PL supply chains, collaboration aspects are some of the ways forward.

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